

Study on different types of media and spawns in *Pleurotus sajor-caju* (Jacq.) Quel. cultivation

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Abstract

Oyster mushroom (*Pleurotus sajor-caju* (Jacq.) Quel.) were collected from Mushroom Research and Technology Development Farm (9 Mile), Yangon Region. In the culture of oyster mushroom, the following four steps were done: preparation of pure culture of mushroom, preparation of mother spawn media, preparation of cultivated spawn bags and cropping of mushroom. Seven different types of agar media were used for the preparation of pure culture mushroom by tissue culture. Four different kinds of raw materials were used for the preparation of mother spawn media. Seven different types of spawn bags are used for the cultivation of spawns. Growth rate of mycelium in each step was observed and recorded daily. In the study of cropping mushroom, the yields of different types of experiments were investigated.

Keywords: Cultivated Mushroom, Mycology trends

Introduction

Oyster mushroom (*P.sajor-caju*) is an edible mushroom having an excellent taste and flavor. It belongs to order Agaricales and Family Tricholomataceae. Mushroom include 14,000 to 22,000 species, among which over 2,000 species are edible and a dozen of them are commercially cultivated (Petal et. Al., 2012). The *Pleurotus* mushroom is also known as Oyster mushroom because the pileus or cap is shell like, spatulate and tongue shaped. Mushroom is defined as a macrofungus with a distinctive fruiting body, large enough to be seen with the naked eyes and to be picked by hand. Unlike green plants, mushrooms cannot generate nutrients by photosynthesis, but take nutrient from other sources. (Song Back Cho, 2004).

The first reliable evidence of mushroom consumption dates back to several hundred years [BC](#) in [China](#). The Chinese value mushrooms for medicinal properties as well as for food. *Pleurotus* genus present high contents of protein, vitamins, minerals and low contents of fat (M, Bonatti, P. karnopp, 2004). Moreover, *Pleurotus* species contents are high in potassium sodium ratio which make mushrooms an ideal food for patient suffering from hypertension and heart disease (Chang, 1996). Mushrooms have become popular throughout the world since they have wonderful food and medicinal values.

Nowadays, the local demand for mushroom is also steadily increasing (Upadgyay, 2011). *Pleurotus* species have become more popular and widely cultivated throughout the world particularly in Asia and Europe as they have simple and low cost production technology and higher bioefficiency. (Chang and Buswell 1969). It is now commercially cultivated in at least 60 countries. China, The United States, Netherlands, France and Poland being the top five producers. (Chang, 1989)

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Oyster mushroom grows naturally in the temperate zone of the cooler seasons. The Oyster mushroom may also grow on decaying organic matter, protein rich food from various agro-waste without composting. The fruiting body of this mushroom is distinctly shell-shaped with different shades of white, cream, grey, yellow, pink or light brown depending upon the species. It is cultivated worldwide and the techniques of mushroom culture have now been widely investigated.

The main propose is to share the mushroom growing methods, to investigate the best media for the culture of mycelium and the best mother spawn, to find out the best composition of spawn media and to know optimum yield of Oyster mushrooms.

Materials and Methods

Identification of mushrooms

Oyster mushroom (*Pleurotus sajor.caju*) was obtained from Mushroom Research and Technology Development (9 Mile), Yangon Region. The mushroom obtained was identified and classified according to Krieger and Shaffer (1967) and Svreek (1998), so as to confirm their identity.

Selection of mushroom (Chang, 1999)

It must have healthy looking, with the pileus curving. The selected mushroom should fresh and not be too mature nor too young. It should be picked in the morning and has not been watered absolutely. It must have a stiff stipe and not contaminated by microorganisms.

Isolation of tissue

About 0.5 cm of the tissue from the connecting point of stipe an pileus of edible mushroom was isolated. The isolated tissue was cultured on six different starch sources agar medium. The growth of mycelium from tissue was observed until the culture bottles were filled with it. The isolation was undertaken according to E.J.Maria Florence and M. Balasundran (2000).

Media used

The composition of each medium used was based on the method of Tuite (1969) and Chang (1996). The six starch media were used, Potato Glucose Agar (PGA), Sweet potato Glucose Agar (SPGA), Corn Glucose Agar (CGA), Tapioca Glucose Agar (TGA), Rice Glucose Agar (RGA), and Arrow root Glucose Agar (ArGA). These six different solid agar media and control medium were used during experimentation for making a comparative study on mycelium growth of Oyster mushroom.

Culture Media Preparation

200g of Potato, Sweet potato, Corn, Tapioca, Rice and Arrow root were washed thoroughly in water and peeled (except corn and rice). They were rinsed with distilled water. The materials (except corn and rice) were cut into equal slices separately, then they were boiled in 500 ml of distilled water. Each extract liquid were collected in the beaker. Into each extract 20 g agar, 20 g glucose and 500 ml distilled water were added. It was stirred occasionally until the agar completely dissolved. About 75 ml of the boiled mixture was poured into the sterilized bottles. These bottles were sterilized in an autoclave at 121 °C for 15 minutes. Sterilized bottles were then placed in the culture room under room temperature.

Table 1. Composition of different starch containing media

Treatments	Materials (Source of starch)	Weight of materials (gm)	Weight of Glucose (gm)	Weight of Agar (gm)	Distilled water (L)
Control	-	-	-	20	1L
PGA	Potato	200	20	20	1L
SPGA	Sweet potato	200	20	20	1L
CGA	Corn	200	20	20	1L
TGA	Tapioca	200	20	20	1L
RGA	Rice	200	20	20	1L
ArGA	Arrow root	200	20	20	1L

Tissue culture of mushroom procedure

The mushroom was thoroughly pre-washed in water. Then it was surface sterilized with 70% ethyl alcohol. The mushroom was then cut lengthwise from the cap downward with disposal sterilize scalpel. The Oyster mushroom was pierced with bare hands. With a disposable sterilized scalpel, a small piece of internal tissue of the pierced mushroom was taken with a long forcep (15 cm) and put onto the agar surface inside the sterilized bottles. Aseptically the mouth of the bottles were plugged with cotton wool according to the method of Pathak, V.N., N. Yadav and M. Gaur 1998.

Culture condition

All culture bottles were incubated at ($32 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$) and (30-35%) relative humidity.

Measurement and recording of mycelium growth

The initial growth of mycelium was recorded by photographs. The growth of mycelium was measured in centimeter (cm) scale daily and the data of mycelium growth in culture bottled were recorded by photographs. The average growth rate of mycelium in five replicates from one experiment was calculated. (Chang, 1999)

Preparation of spawn media (Chang. 1999 and F.A.O, 1983).

Sawdust and grains were used for preparation of Oyster spawn media. The cereal grains and mycelium mixture are called spawn and are also considered to be the mushroom seed. (Maria Florence, E.J. and M. Balasundran., 2000).

Sorghum grains and bean seeds were washed clean and boiled with water until the skin soften. The boiled grains were cooled and mixed with 30% sawdust and 0.5 lime. The mixture was introduced into the bottle until the height of the media became 17 cm and sterilized in an autoclave with 121°C for 35 minutes. Sterilized bottles were allowed to cool and placed in the culture room under room temperature. A small piece of mycelium with Agar from pure culture was placed onto sterilized grain media in culture chamber. The average growth rates of mycelium in three replicates from one experiment were recorded daily.

Table 2. Composition of different spawn media

Treatments	Materials	Sawdust	Lime	Moisture
Control sawdust	100%	-	-	65%
Gram pea	100%	30%	0.5%	65%
Green gram	100%	30%	0.5%	65%
Sorghum	100%	30%	0.5%	65%

Preparation of cultivated spawn bags

The spawn bags were prepared according to the method of Chang 1999, FAO 1993. Rubber sawdust 100%, pea husk 10%, fine rice bran 10%, glucose 1%, Epsom salt 0.02% of ingredients were mixed together and watered to keep the moisture of 65%. The mixture of ingredients were poured into heat-resistant polyethylene bags. The filling and pressing were done till half of the plastic bag was full. The mouth of the bag was grasped and pushed through a plastic collar and pulled up to the bag, then fold it over the collar and tightly sealed with rubber band.

A hole of 3mm diameter was bored down the center in order to promote the rapid penetration of spawn into bags. The bags were plugged with cotton wool, covered with a piece of plastic and sealed with a rubber band. The bags were sterilized in an autoclave 121°C for 35 minutes. About two spoonful of a good mycelium containing in spawn bottle were introduced into the spawn bags.

Then the prepared spawn bags were stacked on racks in a clean room where the temperature of 25°-30°C was maintained. The average growth rates of mycelium in three replicates from one experiment are recorded daily. It took about 25-28 days for the bags to be filled with mycelium. After 7 days, fruiting bodies were formed within the bags.

Table 3. Composition of different spawn bags

Treatment	Sawdust	Pea husk	Lime	Epsom salt	Glucose	Fine rice bran	Moisture
Control, A	100%	-	-	-	-	-	65%
B	100%	-	1%	0.02%	1%	10%	65%
C	100%	10%	-	0.02%	1%	10%	65%
D	100%	10%	1%	-	1%	10%	65%
E	100%	10%	1%	0.02%	-	10%	65%
F	100%	10%	1%	0.02%	1%	-	65%
FFF	100%	10%	1%	0.02%	1%	10%	65%

Cropping of mushrooms

Opening the bags for cropping (P.B. Flegg, 1975)

When the bags were filled with fruiting bodies, collars and cotton plugs were removed and the bags relocated in the cropping house (cropping house should be well ventilated to promote good production of mushrooms).

Watering (P.B. Flegg, 1975)

The bags were sprinkled with a tiny sprayer. The watering frequency depended on the surrounding atmosphere humidity. The moisture content was always maintained at 80-90% relatively humidity. The growth rate of fruiting bodies changing to mature sporophore stages in different kinds of bags were observed and recorded.

Picking period (P.B. Flegg, 1975)

About 3-7 days after the cultivated bags were opened and watered the stage of picking period was reached. Mushrooms were picked when they were fully mature, the edge of the cap unfold and thin out. The picking period differed depending on various substrates.

Results

According to table 4, growth of mycelium was found to start growing after 2 days except Rice Glucose Agar medium which the growth was initiated medium only after 5 days of culture. It took 17-18 days, 21-22 days, 14-15 days, 26-27 days, 29-30 days and 16-17 days for the growth of mycelium to be completely (10 cm) on PGA, SPGA, CGA, TGA, RGA and ArGA respectively. CGA medium was the best medium for the growth of *Pleurotus sajor-caju* mycelium (15 days), while RGA medium showed the longest day for mycelium growth (30 days).

Mother spawn bottles were respectively prepared with Sawdust spawn, Gram pea grain spawn, Green gram grain spawn and Sorghum grain spawn. The mycelium of Sawdust spawn started growing in 19-20 days and completely filled the spawn bottles in 32-33 days. Gram pea grain spawn, Green gram grain spawn and Sorghum grain spawn initiated the growth of mycelium in 1-2 days and completely filled spawn bottles in 21-22 days, 29-30 days and 25-26 days respectively. The Gram pea grain spawn showed the best mycelium of the mother spawn and it was transferred to the cultivated spawn bags.

Table 4. Comparison of mycelium growth on seven Agar media

Days	Mycelium growth (cm)						
	Control	PGA	SPGA	CGA	TGA	RGA	ArGA
1	-	0	0	0	0	0	0
2	-	0.10	0.10	0.14	0.10	0	0.10
3	-	0.34	0.23	0.30	0.30	0	0.50
4	-	0.51	0.32	0.91	0.42	0	1.00
5	-	0.80	0.60	1.12	0.61	0	1.73
6	-	1.12	1.21	2.40	0.85	0.10	2.32
7	-	1.54	1.53	3.00	1.24	0.10	3.00
8	-	2.32	1.70	4.27	1.92	0.21	3.58
9	-	3.00	2.54	5.14	2.37	0.25	4.21
10	-	3.65	3.42	5.82	3.28	0.28	5.40
11	-	4.17	3.85	7.20	3.82	0.31	6.43
12	-	5.03	4.36	7.70	4.23	0.40	7.00
13	-	5.50	5.00	8.42	4.60	0.48	7.56
14	-	6.23	5.51	9.60	5.27	0.56	8.28
15	-	7.30	6.00	10.00	5.64	0.69	8.74
16	-	8.34	6.48	-	6.50	0.76	9.50
17	-	9.23	7.00	-	6.72	0.91	10.00
18	-	10.00	7.50	-	6.93	1.42	-
19	-	-	8.00	-	7.34	2.43	-
20	-	-	8.52	-	7.62	3.21	-
21	-	-	9.27	-	7.81	4.50	-
22	-	-	10.00	-	8.26	5.83	-
23	-	-	-	-	8.60	6.21	-
24	-	-	-	-	8.97	6.80	-
25	-	-	-	-	9.50	7.10	-
26	-	-	-	-	9.82	7.81	-
27	-	-	-	-	10.00	8.63	-
28	-	-	-	-	-	9.10	-
29	-	-	-	-	-	9.60	-
30	-	-	-	-	-	10.00	-

Table 5. Comparison of mycelium growth on four mother spawns

Days	Mycelium growth (cm)			
	Control	Gram pea	Green gram	Sorghum
1	0	0	0	0
2	0	0.50	0.30	0.30
3	0	1.00	0.60	0.60
4	0	1.60	0.90	0.82
5	0	2.00	1.50	1.10
6	0	2.50	2.10	1.80
7	0	3.00	2.70	2.50
8	0	3.50	3.30	3.20
9	0	4.50	3.90	3.90
10	0	5.50	4.50	4.60
11	0	6.50	5.10	5.30
12	0	7.50	5.70	6.00
13	0	8.50	6.30	6.70
14	0	9.50	6.90	7.40
15	0	10.50	7.50	8.10
16	0	11.50	8.10	8.80
17	0	12.50	8.70	9.50
18	0	13.50	9.30	10.20
19	0	14.50	8.50	11.00
20	1.30	15.50	10.50	11.90
21	2.60	16.50	11.20	12.80
22	3.90	17.00	11.90	13.70
23	5.20	-	12.60	14.60
24	6.50	-	13.30	15.50
25	7.80	-	14.00	16.40
26	9.10	-	14.70	17.00
27	10.40	-	15.30	-
28	11.70	-	16.00	-
29	13.00	-	16.70	-
30	14.30	-	17.00	-
31	15.60	-	-	-
32	16.90	-	-	-
33	17.00	-	-	-

In different types of spawn bags, the mycelium started growing in 1-2 days and the spawn bag F was filled with the mycelium in 14-15 days. However, D and E were completely filled in 16-17 days, while A, B, C and FFF were filled with the mycelium in spawn bags in 17-18 days. The spawn bag FFF produced the best appearance of mycelium. After 7 days, the cultivated spawn bags were transferred to the cropping house.

Table 6. Comparison of mycelium growth on spawn bags

Days	Mycelium growth (cm)						
	Control, A	B	C	D	E	F	FFF
1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
2	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.10	1.10	1.00
3	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.20	2.20	2.00
4	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.30	3.30	3.00
5	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.40	4.40	4.00
6	5.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	5.50	5.50	5.00
7	6.00	6.00	6.00	6.00	6.60	6.60	6.00
8	7.20	7.20	7.20	7.20	7.70	7.70	7.00
9	8.50	8.50	8.50	8.50	8.80	8.80	8.00
10	9.50	9.50	9.50	9.50	9.90	10.00	9.00
11	10.50	10.50	10.50	10.90	10.90	11.30	10.00
12	11.50	11.50	11.50	12.00	12.00	13.00	11.00
13	12.50	12.50	12.50	13.10	13.10	14.30	12.00
14	13.50	13.50	13.50	14.20	14.20	15.60	13.00
15	14.50	14.50	14.50	15.30	15.30	17.00	14.00
16	15.50	15.50	15.50	16.40	16.40	-	15.00
17	16.50	16.50	16.50	17.00	17.00	-	16.00
18	17.00	17.00	17.00	-	-	-	17.00
19	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
20	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

Ref; Table 3.

The yield of mushrooms, total weight of Control (A) was 40g, 150g for B, 280g for C, 160 g for D, 120g for E, 90g for F and 310g for FFF in which, the best yield of cultivated spawn bag was FFF among different types of seven spawn bags.

Table 7. Comparison of yield (gm) in different spawn bags

Cropping period	Yield (gm)						
	Control, A	B	C	D	E	F	FFF
I	40	80	150	120	80	60	130
II	-	70	80	30	40	30	100
III	-	-	50	-	-	-	80
Total	40	150	280	160	120	90	310

Discussion and Conclusion

In this study, the tissue of mushroom was inoculated on seven different agar media. The growing mycelium was white, composed with thread like hyphae, which was in agreement with Chang (1999). Seven different agar medium such as Control, Potato Glucose Agar (PGA), Sweet potato Glucose Agar (SPGA), Corn Glucose Agar (CGA), Tapioca Glucose Agar (TGA), Rice Glucose Agar (RGA) and Arrow-root Glucose Agar (ArGA) were undertaken. After two days inoculation of the fresh tissue, mycelium growth started on the each media. On PGA medium in 18 days, SPGA medium in 22 days, CGA medium in 15 days, TGA medium in 27 days, RGA medium in 30 days and ArGA medium in 17 days respectively. Control medium does not show any mycelium while CGA medium showed highest growth rate of mycelium.

Grain spawn was prepared by Sawdust grain spawn, Gram pea grain spawn and Green gram grain spawn and Sorghum grain spawn respectively. The growth of mycelium on Sawdust and grain spawn is agreed with the Chang (1999). The gram pea grain spawn showed the best growth rate of mycelium.

The cultivated spawn bags (FFF) were prepared by using with Sawdust 100%, Pea husk 10%, Lime 1%, Epson salt 0.02%, Glucose 1%, Fine rice bran 10% and moisture 65% proportionally. The absence of Pea husk in B, Lime in C, Epson salt in D, Glucose in E and Fine rice barn in F. In which the spawn bag of Control (A) contained only Sawdust and water. The best growth rate of mycelium in spawn bags was FFF because it contained all kind of nutrients. The mycelium growth on rubber sawdust is agreed with the E.J.Maria Florence and M. Balasundran (2000).

It can be concluded that *Pleurotus sajor-caju* (Jacq.) (Quel.) is suitable for food and medicine. The technique and methods are economical and not much difficult in rural areas where raw materials and facilities required are easily available. It should be cultivated for mass production and preserved in dry form for prolong use of consumption.

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Appendix

Appendix Figure 1. Preparation of seven different agar media

Appendix Figure 2. Measure the mycelium

Appendix Figure 3. Preparation of spawn bottles and filled with the mycelium